

FIBER FRACTURE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The role of fiber fracture in the degradation and failure of composite laminates is addressed. Significant accomplishments in the areas of modelling and characterization are surveyed. Results of recent experimental initiatives to study fiber fracture *in situ* are presented. Directions for future research are identified and discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Failure of composite laminates of practical interest is frequently dominated by the accumulation of fiber fractures. Our knowledge however of the details of these microscopic events and of the way in which this mode of damage influences and is influenced by matrix-related damage modes is limited. The characterization of fiber fracture poses a challenge to those who seek to develop predictive models of strength and lifetime for fiber-dominated composites.

A substantial body of research in the general area of fiber mechanics exists. This work spans over thirty years and includes many contributors. With some exceptions, this work has focused on modelling and analyzing fiber behavior on the scale of a single fiber or fiber bundle, or as a unidirectional layer of fibers. Significant, fundamental advances in describing fiber fracture due to tensile loading have resulted.

The purpose of the present paper is to review some of the significant research in the area of fiber fracture and to identify where possible those areas of concensus which may be leading to a unified understanding of the broader issue of failure in fiber-dominated composite laminates. The focus here will be restricted to brittle fiber composites. Both analytical and experimental treatments will be surveyed. Results of recent efforts to study fiber fracture in situ will be presented. Areas in which further research would, in the opinion of the author, yield significant advantage in predicting composite failure will be identified.

BACKGROUND

Some of the earliest work on fiber fracture has been the most enduring. The inclusion of fiber strength variability in a unidirectional failure theory by Rosen [1] led to the now-familiar chain of bundles model. This model was subsequently used by Zweben [2] and Rosen and Zweben [3] to postulate the role of individual fiber fracture in a cumulative process leading to overall lamina fracture. This work collectively has served as the basis for many of the analyses which followed. It also utilized and thereby perhaps popularized the Weibull distribution function for treating fiber strength variability [4]. Another fundamental work was the treatment of load sharing among fibers in the neighborhood of a broken fiber advanced by Hedgepeth and Van Dyke [5]. Their approach has been used directly or in a modified form in many cumulative damage models.

As one views the treatment of fiber fracture in failure theories collectively several approaches can be identified. The work on single fibers and dry bundles, i.e., those not impregnated with a matrix material, is represented for example by Daniels [6] and Coleman [7] who provided the mathematical basis from which nearly all statistically-based failure

theories proceed. The behavior of bundles of fibers in the dry state and in the impregnated state may of course be different and the relationship must be known. Manders and Chou [8] analyzed the strength variation of carbon and glass fibers in both dry bundle and epoxy-impregnated states. They found that impregnated tows of fibers exhibited strength two and one half times higher than that of unimpregnated fibers from the same batch. They explained this increase in terms of a difference in the probability of failure function for fibers in the impregnated condition. Manders and Chou [9] and Chi and Chou [10] hypothesized and demonstrated respectively that by prestressing dry bundles of carbon fibers prior to impregnation a small increase in composite strength and a substantial reduction in composite strength variability could be achieved. These improvements in strength, attributed to pre-fracture of the weakest fibers, appear to derive from suppression of dynamic stress waves which would otherwise have propagated upon failure of those fibers.

The incorporation of load-sharing protocols is central to the issue of extending single fiber failure models to the prediction of lamina failure. Hedgepeth [11] used a shear lag analysis to formulate one of the early load-sharing rules for an infinite, two-dimensional array of fibers under tensile load. His model provided a "stress concentration factor" to be applied to fibers adjacent to one or more broken fibers. He also considered the dynamic overstress resulting from the failure of one or more simultaneous fiber breaks and reported that this dynamic effect increased the static overload by fifteen percent for one fiber break up to a limiting value of twenty-seven percent. Zweben incorporated this rule in describing distinct modes of failure which can occur in unidirectional plies: a cumulative mode in which significant numbers of dispersed fiber fractures occur in a stable configuration prior to ply failure; and a

non-cumulative mode in which relatively few fiber fractures precede lamina failure. In the former category he placed glass-epoxy material; in the latter, boron-epoxy. The non-cumulative model of failure is dominated by fiber strength. The cumulative mode is influenced by the environment which exists in the material near a broken fiber and hence introduces matrix and interface involvement in the overall failure process. Rosen and Zweben suggested in subsequent work [3] that, although their analysis for cumulative failure did not yield a failure criterion directly, a practical and conservative criterion could be associated with the stress at which the first multiple fracture occurred. Herring et.al. [12] studied cumulative and non-cumulative failure in a boron-aluminum composite. In a remarkable series of radiographs, details of these failure modes were identified including evidence of shattering of fibers by shock waves generated in fracture of adjacent fibers. Mullins et.al. [13] fabricated composites of boron-epoxy and graphite-epoxy which were caused to fail cumulatively, non-cumulatively, or by combinations of these modes by modifying the matrix and interface properties and thereby demonstrated the significance of these properties on fiber fracture mode.

Redistribution of stress in hybrid composites has been treated by Fukuda and Chou [14]. Using shear lag analysis of hybrid plies in which low modulus and high modulus fibers were intermingled, they predicted that the stress concentration factor on the high modulus fibers adjacent to broken fibers would be lower than that for an all-high modulus fiber composite under the same conditions. They thereby provided an additional basis for explaining the so-called hybrid effect by which high modulus fibers exhibit a higher strain to failure when hybridized with low modulus fibers.

In formulating load sharing rules, it is normally necessary to model the fiber arrangement. This is frequently taken to be a square or hexagonal array of fibers in a repeating pattern. Batdorf [15] has examined the implications of assuming uniform alignment and spacing of fibers. In applying Weibull theory to predict unidirectional composite failure, agreement with experimental data [16] could be achieved only if stress concentration factors as postulated by Hedgepeth and Van Dyke were assumed to also follow a Weibull distribution.

Efforts to develop load-sharing rules ultimately revolve about the more basic issue of analyzing stress fields in the vicinity of broken fibers. The elasticity problem posed by such a condition can be of considerable complexity depending upon the degree to which the material and damage inhomogeneity is included. Goree and Gross [17,18] have used the material modelling approach of Zweben [19] to calculate the stresses in the vicinity of one or more broken fibers. They simplified the elasticity problem somewhat by including only certain components of stress and were thus able to include matrix yielding and splitting in their analysis. Their predictions of unidirectional strength compared favorably to experiments on notched metal matrix and brittle matrix composites. The use of notched unidirectional specimens to simulate the condition of a composite having load-induced multiple fiber fractures has not been adequately studied to establish these as realistically equivalent conditions. Experiment lags analysis substantially in this area.

Phoenix and Harlow [20-22] have formulated an essentially exact solution for the two-dimensional stress field in the presence of broken fibers and have significantly refined the relationship between specific load-sharing rules and predicted composite strength. The rigor expressed in their analysis was achieved by restricting the geometry to a somewhat idealized case.

In the present context, the ultimate issue is predicting lamina failure from a microstructural analysis. There have been numerous uniaxial failure theories advanced since the early work of Rosen and Zweben. Although the analyses vary in their generality and hence their complexity, a number of common themes are shared: fiber fractures are viewed initially as random events with a probability of occurrence described by a strength distribution function; the occurrence of subsequent fiber fractures are seen as increasingly influenced by existing breaks and this influence is expressed in terms of static and/or dynamic load sharing; and the development of some critical number or arrangement of broken fibers is seen as the "triggering mechanism" for cascading fiber fracture and thereby composite failure. The models differ in the main in their rigor in treating the complex elasticity problem posed by the presence of one or more broken fibers in a three-dimensional array of unbroken fibers imbedded in a second medium which may itself include discontinuities.

Batdorf [23,24] sought a simpler formulation of the problem than that addressed by Phoenix and Harlow by choosing to focus on the development of a critical Griffith-type flaw consisting of multiple adjacent fiber fractures. While retaining the Weibull strength distribution in accounting for individual fiber response, his analysis abandoned the chain-of-bundles model and instead treated the stability of "multiplets" of broken fibers. Composite failure is then predicted upon the first occurrence of a critical multiplet at the applied stress. In order for this theory to be of practical use, a number of parameters inherent in the formulation and related to matrix damage (disbonding and cracking in the vicinity of a multiplet for example) and stress redistribution around and among multiplets must be quantified. By making some simplifying assumptions regarding these parameters, Batdorf and Ghaffarian [25] reported good

agreement between the model's predictions and experimental results on tows and laminated coupons of graphite-epoxy [26].

The concept of a critical flaw appears in fact in many unidirectional strength theories. It is generally recognized that given the microstructural scale involved, attempts to predict composite strength by applying linear elastic fracture mechanics methodologies to a flaw comprised of adjacent fiber breaks are inappropriate and unrewarded. Instead, probability arguments must replace the more familiar idea of self-similar growth of a dominant crack in describing composite failure. Stochastic treatments incorporating critical flaw concepts are reflected in the work of Bolotin [27], Ovchinskii et.al. [28] and Tamuzs [29,30]. These treatments are differentiated principally in the methods and extent to which load redistribution and matrix-related damage are treated. Manders et.al. [31] used Monte Carlo simulations of the failure process in three-dimensional fiber composites to study the influence of fiber strength variability on composite strength variability and critical flaw size. They found that unless the fibers are very uniform in strength, a single fiber fracture was not sufficient for composite failure. For typical fiber variability, a flaw of three to five broken fibers was required for composite failure.

EXPERIMENTAL EVIDENCE

The study of fiber fracture in the pursuit of a unified failure theory is difficult in the abstract and formidable in reality. Although many of the analytical treatments surveyed in this paper are linked in some way to experimental observations, it can reasonably be said that experiment lags theory in this area by a considerable margin. There have been some notable successes beginning with the work of Zweben who used the birefringent property of glass fibers to locate both fiber breaks and stress concentrations. Because fibers of practical interest are small in diameter, closely

packed in three dimensions and difficult to resolve by conventional nondestructive techniques, the cumulative fiber fracture condition preceding failure is difficult to define. Recent refinements in eddy current methods [32] hold some promise for the prospect of detecting groups of fractures in carbon fiber composites.

A destructive method for exposing fiber fracture for a variety of fibers in organic matrix composite has been developed by Freeman [33]. By this technique a laminate is heated to a temperature sufficient to partially pyrolyze the matrix. The interlaminar bond strength is thereby diminished to the point that the individual laminae can be separated. When the laminate is unstacked in this way, the individual fibers adjacent to the interfaces are exposed. Sufficient matrix material remains intact to hold these fibers in place even if they were previously fractured. Thus a picture of fiber fracture distribution in situ is presented for examination.

This author and colleagues have used this technique extensively to study fiber fracture resulting from static and cyclic loading of graphite-epoxy laminates. Much of this work focused on damage coupling in cross-ply and quasistropic laminates [34-37]. In the present context only those portions dealing with unidirectional laminates merit survey. It was discovered that the deply technique permitted the unstacking of plies even in unidirectional laminates where the interfaces were differentiated as resin-rich zones, a result of fabrication from prepreg material.

In a typical study, specimens were loaded individually to various fractions of the mean ultimate strength, \bar{S}_{ult} . They were then unloaded, cut into smaller coupons, and depled in the manner previously described. Plies from these coupons were examined in a scanning electron microscope. A photomicrograph of a typical analysis area is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. SEM photomicrograph of fibers in a deplied graphite-epoxy lamina

Depending upon the nature of the study, twelve - to fifteen hundred such areas would be examined for each specimen. By counting individual fiber fractures and averaging over all observations for one specimen, it was possible to compute fiber fracture density (fiber fractures/mm²). By examining specimens representing the full range of loading, the relationship between load and fiber fracture density could be determined. Typical curves are shown in figure 2. It is possible to repeat this procedure for fibers located away from the interface by removing fibers layer-by-layer with adhesive tape. In the instances where this was done selectively, there was no measurable difference in fiber fracture density for the unidirectional laminate and a marked decrease for the cross-ply laminate.

It was also possible and potentially valuable in consideration of the theoretical prediction of cumulative failure to analyze the frequency of occurrence of multiple adjacent fiber fractures. An example of this accounting is shown in figure 3. Adopting Batdorf's terminology in naming

Figure 2. Fiber fracture density versus tensile load for unidirectional and cross-ply graphite-epoxy laminates.

groups of adjacent fiber fractures as singlets, doublets, triplets and higher order multiplets [23], the trend observed in unidirectional graphite-epoxy laminates suggested that if a critical size multiplet indeed triggered laminate failure then the size of that multiplet was on the order of five or six adjacent fiber breaks. That is to say that from extensive examination of damaged but unfailed unidirectional laminates, there did not occur a multiplet as defined here of order greater than four even for laminates loaded above the mean laminate strength. Critical multiplets on this order have been predicted by Curtis [38] for a graphite-epoxy laminate based on a Monte Carlo simulation of a strain-based failure criterion. A critical multiplet on this order has also been predicted and observed by Manders and Bader [39,40].

PROSPECTS

Although the issue of micromechanically-based failure models for

Figure 3. Frequency of occurrence of fiber fracture multipliers in tensile loading of unidirectional graphite-epoxy laminates

tensile failure of laminates is far from settled, the convergence of analytical approaches and the emergence of experimental techniques offers encouragement. In practical terms, however, a unidirectional failure model represents only a first step, albeit an important one, in understanding and predicting the response of more complicated composite structures. The list of issues to be addressed is a long and expanding one. Among the important unresolved issues in the author's opinion are: compressive failure, multiaxial loading, long term effects such as fatigue and environment, development of non-destructive evaluation techniques for the identification of interior fiber fracture in thick and/or opaque laminates, and damage coupling and load redistribution in multidirectional laminates. This last issue may have important implications in determining how a unidirectional failure theory can be transferred to a more general laminate. If damage in off-axis plies can be modelled in such a way that load shedding in those plies can be translated relatively simply into an increase in the global stress of the 0 degree plies, then the theory may translate fairly simply. But if load redistribution is localized by adjacent ply damage, then unidirectional failure theories must be modified

to account for non-uniform stress in the critical loading-bearing plies. This stress variation would be superposed on the non-uniform stresses arising from fiber fractures. Evidence of the effect of matrix cracks on fiber fracture in graphite-epoxy laminates can be seen in figure 4. Shown is the locus of fiber fractures in a 0 degree ply taken from a $[0, \pm 45]_S$ laminate which had been subjected to tension fatigue loading. The

Figure 4. SEM photomicrograph of a deplied graphite-epoxy lamina showing fiber fracture localization

Localization of fiber fracture along the 45 degree line, caused by a crack in the adjacent 45 degree ply, is characteristic not only of this laminate but of several other laminate stacking sequences studied [36]. The effect has been observed as well in static tensile loading, but the density of fiber breaks is lower in that case and the zone in which they occur not as localized as for fatigue. The influence of this localization on strength has not to the author's knowledge been studied extensively.

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